

Research Article

Motivation and Impulse in E-Shopping Among Pre-Service Teachers: Needs-Based vs. Wants-Based

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Article History	Abstract
<p>Received: January 20, 2026 Accepted: February 10, 2026 Published: February 17, 2026</p>	<p>Motivation and impulse in e-shopping among pre-service teachers reflects the tension between needs-based and wants-based consumption in an increasingly digital marketplace. This research examines the items most commonly purchased online by pre-service teachers of Saint Louis University, how frequently they shop online, and how promotional offers, discounts, or advertisements influence their impulse buying behavior. A mixed-method design was used, combining a checklist and a 7-point Likert scale to quantify product categories and shopping frequency, with a focus group discussion to explore how online promotions trigger unplanned purchases. Clothing and accessories emerged as the most frequently purchased items, followed by educational products, and beauty and self-care indicating that wants-based, hedonic motivations dominate even as needs-based, utilitarian purchases remain important. Most respondents report shopping online every few months, suggesting that e-shopping functions as an occasional but established habit rather than a daily routine. Thematic analysis showed that academic and personal needs, perceived savings, anticipated future use, and a sense of urgency from limited-time offers interact to stimulate impulse buying among pre-service teachers. Overall, the study finds that their e-shopping is primarily wants-based, with promotional strategies amplifying impulsive purchases and highlighting the need for responsible online consumption.</p> <p>Keywords: E-Shopping, Pre-Service Teachers, Impulse Buying, Needs-Based, Wants-Based, Promotional Strategies.</p>

Introduction

Shopping is an essential part of the economy, as it drives demand for products and services. It allows businesses to generate revenue while consumers fulfill their needs or desires. For individuals, shopping is a way to acquire items for daily living, entertainment, or self-expression (Cobrief, 2025). According to Cobrief (2025), shopping is the activity of buying goods or services, typically from a store or online. It involves browsing for products, selecting items to purchase, and completing the transaction. Shopping can be done for personal use, to fulfill needs, or for business purposes, and it can take place in physical stores, markets, or through digital platforms such as e-commerce websites or mobile apps.

For this reason, shopping plays a significant role in people's lives by fulfilling basic needs such as food, clothing, and shelter, while also enhancing our quality of life through greater choice and convenience. It serves as both a social and leisure activity that brings emotional satisfaction and enjoyment. Beyond personal benefits, shopping drives the economy by generating jobs and supporting industries, and it allows consumers to express their values through ethical consumption. However, responsible shopping through planning, budgeting, and making sustainable choices is essential to ensure it remains a positive force (Saini, 2024). Shopping fulfills

essential needs while simultaneously stimulating economic activity and enabling personal expression. A prominent contemporary iteration of this activity is e-shopping. According to Tang *et al.*, (2021), e-shopping is the process whereby customers directly buy goods or services from a seller in real time over the internet. Moreover, shopping online becomes an alternative for consumers because it is easier (Capitulo and Yturralde, 2025), as most consumers today seek methods to simplify their purchases. Since its inception, e-shopping has grown rapidly around the world. People's attitudes about e-shopping have shifted with the COVID-19 pandemic and as a result of the quarantine imposed in countries (Obeidat, *et al.*, 2024). According to the International Trade Administration (2024), the top Philippine e-commerce platforms are Shopee, Lazada, Zalora, and BeautyMNL. Other known e-shopping platforms in the Philippines include Temu, Shein, Nike, TikTok Shop, Carousell PH, eBay, Facebook marketplace, etc.

People indulge in online purchases because they are motivated by certain factors. Motivation is defined as the reason which causes or encourages someone to act or behave in a particular way. It is also defined as a person's willingness to strive to achieve or fulfill their emotional needs (Asnawati and Wahyuni, 2018). Shopping motivation is a force that motivates customers to take shopping actions to achieve a goal, desire, or satisfy a certain need (Nguyen and Nguyen, 2023). Shopping motivation is specifically divided into two: utilitarian and hedonic motivation (Ha, 2020). Hedonic shopping motivation is a person's desire to shop to fulfill psychological needs, namely emotion, satisfaction, prestige, and other subjective feelings. Consequently, it appears to meet excessive social, aesthetic, and lifestyle demands. It also occurs due to a person's emotional response, sensory pleasure, and dreams (Cinjarevic *et al.*, 2011).

According to Arul Rajan (2020) and Ribeiro Coimbra *et al.*, (2023), hedonic shopping motivation is consumers' motivation to shop because shopping is a pleasure in itself, so they do not pay attention to the benefits of the products purchased. Hedonic purchasing motives relate to individuals' emotional needs for enjoyable and interesting shopping experiences (Kaczmarek, 2017; Arul Rajan, 2020; Dewi and Ang, 2015). According to Mothersbaugh *et al.*, (2020), there are six hedonic shopping motives, these are: (1) adventure shopping, which refers to shopping for fun and adventurous and related to the need for stimulation, (2) social shopping, which involves people who shop just to hang out with friends, (3) gratification shopping, which is related to shopping to reduce stress or as a self-reward and related to the need to reduce tension, (4) idea shopping which involves shopping to follow trends and fashion and is related to the need for categorization and objectification, (5) role shopping which refers to shopping only to give to other people, such as buying gifts, and (6) value shopping which refers to shopping only to look for discounts where the goods are not necessarily needed.

Dewi and Ang (2015) argue that utilitarian purchasing motives are task-oriented, efficient, rational, and intentional rather than an entertaining experience. In other words, utilitarian shopping motivation involves the traditional information processing purchasing model, the buyer is a rational decision-maker who wants to maximize utility by focusing on the tangible benefits of the product (Arul Rajan, 2020; Ribeiro Coimbra *et al.*, 2023). Utilitarian shopping motives have the following categories: (1) achievement shopping which relates to the behavior of visiting an online store where the most important thing is to get the planned item, (2) anticipated utility which refers to the behavior of visiting online stores to get new brands, replace old brands, to get a new image for themselves or their home, or to make one as the first person to have the latest products and fashion, (3) role enactment which refers to the behavior of visiting online stores and shopping very carefully as a responsibility to their role as a housewife, hunting for goods to find cheaper products, and comparing prices to find the best product according to her financial condition, and (4) efficient shopping which refers to the behavior of visiting an online shop to easily find the right goods that suit your wishes in a short or quick time. In the creative-economy era, new ideas are the source of success (Dewi and Ang, 2015; Mothersbaugh *et al.*, 2020; Ribeiro *et al.*, 2023).

Motivations, whether utilitarian or hedonic, drive consumers to engage in shopping activities, seeking to fulfill specific goals, desires, or needs. Building on this understanding of shopping motivations, it is important to consider the phenomenon of impulse buying, where consumers deviate from planned purchases and make spontaneous, often emotionally driven decisions to acquire goods or services without prior intention. Impulse buying is a type of unplanned shopping behavior that occurs when a customer purchases an item without any prior intention or planning. It is often a result of emotional triggers, such as excitement, boredom, stress, or social influence, that override the rational decision-making process. Impulse buying can occur in a physical store or an online marketplace, and it can involve different products, from small accessories to expensive items. Moreover, this type of buying is a sudden, unexpected buying driven by a consumer's impulsive desire to buy, typically sparked by outside stimuli (Chaudhary *et al.*, 2025). Verhagen and Van Dolen (2011) reported that impulsive buying is an irrational behavior associated with spontaneous and unplanned spending. It also means

the sudden buying of goods and services without first meeting the initially planned needs (Suryawardani *et al.*, 2017).

Impulse buying, driven by emotion and spontaneity, contrasts with needs-based shopping. While impulse buys stem from immediate feelings, needs-based shopping addresses recognized deficiencies, prompting problem-solving to fulfill essential requirements. According to Niosi (2021), a need is a basic deficiency given a particular essential item. Consumer behavior can be thought of as the combination of efforts and results related to the consumer's need to solve problems. Consumer problem-solving is triggered by the identification of an unmet need. Moreover, a motive for online shopping is utilitarian, where shoppers focus on solving their needs (Sarkar, 2011; Menoe and Barnard, 2020). Furthermore, it was noted that those who shop for needs buying motives include convenience-seeking, variety seeking, searching for quality of merchandise, reasonable prices, etc.

Needs-based shopping is characterized by a focus on fulfilling essential requirements; however, alternative motivational frameworks prioritize personal preferences and the pursuit of enjoyable, emotionally-driven experiences (Menoe and Barnard, 2020; Niosi, 2021). On the other hand, according to Niosi (2021), a want is placing certain personal criteria as to how that need must be fulfilled. Sarkar (2011), as cited by Menoe and Barnard (2020), defined a buyer whose purpose is to seek pleasure as "Hedonic shoppers". Consequently, these consumers' buying motives are related to the emotional needs of individuals for enjoyable and interesting shopping experiences. This type of consumption involves emotional arousal taking place while purchasing or consuming. Taking all of these into account, this study seeks to provide insights into the online shopping motivations and behaviors of pre-service teachers of Saint Louis University. Hence, this study aims to examine whether the motivation and impulse behind e-shopping among pre-service teachers are primarily needs-based or wants-based.

Significance of the Study

This research addresses the growing trend of e-shopping and its specific implications, for pre-service teachers, a demographic heavily reliant on online platforms for both educational and personal needs. While existing literature explores general online shopping motivations, a gap exists in understanding the nuanced factors driving e-shopping behavior among this specific group. By examining the interplay of needs-based versus wants-based motivations and the influence of marketing tactics on impulse buying, this study provides targeted insights into the consumer psychology of future educators.

The findings offer practical applications for pre-service teachers themselves, empowering them to develop greater awareness of their online spending habits and make more informed financial decisions. Furthermore, the research contributes to a broader understanding of consumer behavior in the digital age, particularly regarding the impact of promotional strategies and the motivations behind unplanned purchases. By identifying the key drivers of e-shopping among pre-service teachers, this study can inform interventions aimed at promoting responsible online consumption and financial well-being within this important segment of society.

Statement of the Problem

The study aims to examine whether the motivation and impulse behind e-shopping among pre-service teachers are primarily needs-based or wants-based. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

- 1) What kind of items are most commonly purchased by pre-service teachers online?
- 2) How frequently do pre-service teachers shop online?
- 3) How do promotional offers, discounts, or advertising influence the impulse buying behavior of pre-service teachers?

Method

This study uses a mixed-methods approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative methods to understand the motivations behind e-shopping and impulse buying behavior. The study quantified data utilizing a checklist to determine the most commonly purchased items by pre-service teachers and how frequently they shop online. On the other hand, a focus group discussion (FGD) was facilitated to determine how promotional offers, discounts, or advertising influence the impulse buying behavior of pre-service teachers. Furthermore, mixed-methods is a research methodology that combines both qualitative and quantitative research approaches to gain a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of a research problem. It goes beyond the limitations of using a single method and allows researchers to leverage the

strengths of both qualitative and quantitative data in a complementary manner. By using a mix of qualitative and quantitative methods, researchers can explore different facets of the research question, leading to a more comprehensive and robust analysis (Saraswati and Devi, 2023).

According to Saraswati and Devi (2023), qualitative research involves collecting data that is non-numeric in nature, such as interviews, focus groups, observations, or open-ended survey responses. Qualitative methods allow researchers to explore subjective experiences, opinions, motivations, and underlying reasons behind certain behaviors. On the other hand, quantitative research involves collecting data in numerical form and using statistical analysis to identify patterns, relationships, and generalizability. Surveys, experiments, and structured observations are common quantitative methods. These methods provide a broader understanding of the research topic, often involving a larger sample size.

Population and Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at Saint Louis University, Baguio City, Philippines, specifically within the School of Teacher Education. The respondents were the pre-service teachers from Saint Louis University.

Data Gathering

The primary data gathering tools are a checklist, a 7-point Likert scale, and an interview guide with a specific question. A checklist is a prepared list of items, requirements, behaviors, actions, or skills, the presence or absence of which is ticked or marked as Yes/No. It can be used for quick and easy recording of the information (Philip, 2024). On the other hand, interview guides are a list of the topics and questions an interviewer plans to cover during an interview. This is an effective tool for maintaining consistency and direction during an interview, and they can range from highly structured interviews to relatively informal conversations (Indeed Editorial Team, 2025). A Likert scale is a five (or seven) -point scale that is used to allow an individual to express how much they agree or disagree with a particular statement. It provides possible answers to a statement or question that allows respondents to indicate their positive-to-negative strength of agreement or strength of feeling regarding the question or statement (McLeod, 2023).

Data Analysis

Data for this research were gathered through a mixed-method design that combined a checklist of 20 product categories, a 7-point Likert scale on shopping frequency, and a focus group discussion (FGD) with pre-service teachers. Checklist and Likert responses were summarized using frequencies, averaging, tallying, and calculating percentages to identify the most commonly purchased items online and the typical intervals at which respondents' shop, thereby describing whether their behavior reflects wants-based or needs-based motivations. Qualitative data from the FGD were transcribed and analyzed using thematic analysis to interpret how promotional offers, discounts, and advertisements influence impulse buying behavior.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows that clothing and accessories are the most commonly purchased items online (96%), which suggest that fashion-related products continue to dominate the e-commerce consumer behavior of the pre-service teachers. This is followed by educational products (80%) and beauty and self-care items (68%), which indicates that online platforms are also widely used for academic needs and personal grooming. On the other hand, compact appliances (20%), baby and toddler products (12%), and other categories (8%) register much lower frequencies.

Table 1. Kind/s of item/s usually purchased online.

Product category	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Clothing and accessories	48	96%
Educational products	40	80%
Beauty and self-care	34	68%
Compact appliances	10	20%
Baby and toddler	6	12%
Others	4	8%

The e-commerce fashion industry has become the most purchased category online, fueled by the accessibility of clothing, accessories, and footwear through online platforms. According to PCMI (2024), based on the number of consumers who prefer to buy products online, fashion, specifically clothes and footwear, are ranked as the most popular among Filipino online shoppers. Furthermore, in the Philippines, most purchased products are fashion (clothes and footwear), with 69% (PCMI, 2024). The other category, which accounts for

8% of items usually purchased online, represents products that do not fit neatly into the major categories listed. This implies that the pre-service teachers of Saint Louis University are influenced by consumer trends related to clothing and accessories. The easy availability of these items through online platforms highlights the strong preference for fashion products among the pre-service teachers in their online shopping habits.

Furthermore, as defined by Menoe and Barnard (2020), hedonic shoppers were found to exist in the online environment for information gathering purposes such as ongoing hobby-type searches, involvement with a product category, positive sociality and surprise, and bargain hunting. Therefore, shopping for clothing and accessories, beauty, and self-care items is considered wants-based. On the other hand, educational products fall under the category of needs. According to Menoe and Barnard (2020), the utilitarian shoppers focus on problem-solving the buyer's need, which, in this case, is the pre-service teachers' shop for their specific education needs. Hence, the pre-service teachers' shopping behavior is primarily focused on their wants, with two of the most commonly purchased items being want-based.

Table 2. Frequency of shopping online.

Response	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Daily	2	4%
Several times a week	8	16%
Once a week	5	10%
Twice a month	11	22%
Once a month	8	16%
Every few months	14	28%
Once a year or less	2	4%

Table 2 implies that only a small portion of respondents shop online daily (4%) or several times a week (16%), indicating that very frequent online shopping is not common among the group. A slightly larger share shop online once a week (10%) or twice a month (22%), suggesting that several respondents integrate online shopping into their regular monthly routine. The highest proportion of respondents falls under the category, every few months (28%), showing that occasional online shopping is the most typical behavior. Meanwhile, once a month (18%) also accounts for a considerable portion, reinforcing that many participants shop online at moderate but not frequent intervals. Lastly, only 4% shop online once a year or less, indicating that very infrequent online shopping is uncommon among the participants.

From the given data, we can see that people tend to shop frequently. In 2022, IPC reported that nearly 80% of online buyers shop at least once per month, and nearly 50% of them shop once every two weeks. Around 22% claim to shop once a week. Research in America was conducted, and it was found that 30% of Americans shop online at least once per month, with 21% doing so two to three times monthly. Another 14% make weekly purchases, and 5% shop daily (Karr, 2025). Similarly, this indicates that the pre-service teachers at Saint Louis University generally shop online every few months, suggesting that occasional online shopping, like a few times per year, is their most common pattern.

Table 3 shows that academic and personal needs, perceived savings, future use, and sense of urgency are ways through which promotional offers, discounts, or advertisements influence the impulsive buying behavior of pre-service teachers. According to Lestari and Dalimunthe (2023), there is an impact of online promotion and discounts on impulse buying. The simultaneous presence of online promotions and discounts amplifies their combined influence, underscoring the synergistic nature of these factors in driving impulse buying behavior. Moreover, academic and personal needs state that impulse buying occurs when the consumer perceives the purchase as fulfilling an immediate need. According to Meena (2018), as cited in Santisi *et al.*, (2021), "despite being aware of the negative effects of buying, there is an enormous desire to immediately satisfy your most pressing needs." This indicates that discounts and sales amplify impulse buying when seen as fulfilling personal or academic needs.

In addition, perceived savings suggests that people often buy things on impulse because they think they are saving money. Price discounts are viewed as an advantage, leading to the perception of consumers getting more value for their money (Utama *et al.*, 2025). This implies that discounts drive impulse buying by making consumers feel they are gaining extra value, making them purchase the deal. This idea is also supported by an article by GeeksforGeeks (2025), stating that consumers are often motivated to make purchases based on the perceived savings a product offers. The belief that a product will provide long-term savings can drive impulsive buying decisions as consumers seek value and cost-effectiveness. On the other hand, future use has a similar

concept, as consumers buy impulsively when they feel the product saves money now and will be useful down the line. Lastly, a sense of urgency drives consumers to make purchases because limited-time deals and payday sales create a feeling that they must buy before they expire. According to Jain (2023), by creating a sense of urgency, such as limited-time offers or low stock warnings, sellers can encourage consumers to make a quick decision. Hence, promotional offers and discounts do instill a sense of urgency, pushing consumers to buy before the deals disappear.

Table 3. Thematic analysis of how promotional offers, discounts, or advertisements influence impulse buying behavior as a pre-service teacher.

Theme	Responses
Academic and personal needs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) <i>Promotional advertisements make me want to buy products that will bring out my full potential. "I like products that could help me with learning. When I see advertisements and discounts, I want to take advantage of them because I want to do well in school."</i> 2) <i>In school, I want what I have to be of high quality and have good materials.</i>
Perceived savings	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) <i>For me, they influence me, as when I see them, I feel like I'm saving money.</i> 2) <i>Whenever I buy, especially items needed for my academics like notebooks, the more vouchers, products, in a positive sense, I get them at a lower price.</i>
Future use	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) <i>If I see something that has a nice deal, I easily buy it without thinking because of the promotions they give me. School supplies, decorations, maybe I will be using them soon. It may be piled up for a long period of time, but I'll still buy it because I might use it soon, until it is needed.</i> 2) <i>Even if it's not a necessity, when you see it and feel like you will need it in the future, you'll get the trigger for impulse buying.</i>
Sense of urgency	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) <i>When you see promo offers, I think it triggers the impulse to buy. You don't plan until you see it.</i> 2) <i>The more promos, the more impulse to buy, which affects me negatively, as it urges me to want to buy more.</i>

Overall, these themes show that the impulsive buying behavior of the pre-service teachers of Saint Louis University is influenced by a combination of academic and personal needs, perceived savings, anticipated future use, and a sense of urgency triggered by promotional offers and discounts. These factors interplay to increase the urge to purchase impulsively, as discounts not only satisfy needs but also create a perception of value and long-term benefit. The presence of limited-time offers further accelerates decision-making, pushing a consumer mindset focused on buying before the offers run out.

To synthesize, the pre-service teachers show a clear influence from consumer trends, specifically clothing and accessories. Their preference for fashion-related products is manifested in their e-shopping patterns, making them primarily wants-based when purchasing online. In relation to this, their e-shopping frequency is more so every few months, suggesting that shopping online only a few times per year is their most common behavior.

Finally, their impulsive buying is influenced by academic and personal needs, along with other factors like perceived savings and future use. Promotional offers and discounts also create urgency, causing spontaneous purchases. This combination of needs, value, and incentives shapes their online shopping behavior.

Conclusion

The findings showed that the most commonly purchased items are clothing and accessories. This meant that fashion-related products continue to dominate the online shopping behavior of the pre-service teachers. Also included are beauty and self-care, and educational products. With clothing and accessories, as well as beauty and self-care, determined that the pre-service teachers' shopping behavior is primarily wants-based.

Furthermore, most of the respondents shop every few months, which implies that occasional online shopping is the most typical behavior for pre-service teachers. Lastly, it was determined that academic and personal needs, perceived savings, future use, and sense of urgency are ways through which promotional offers, discounts, or advertisements influence the impulsive buying behavior of pre-service teachers of Saint Louis University.

Recommendations

For Pre-Service Teachers

Pre-service teachers are encouraged to practice more mindful and intentional online shopping by pausing before making purchases, especially when there is a sale, and considering whether an item is truly needed or simply appealing because of a discount. Setting a simple budget management system can help reduce impulsive buying triggered by promotional offers. Being aware of these habits can support students in managing their finances more responsibly while still enjoying the convenience of online platforms.

For Future Researchers

Future researchers are encouraged to expand the study to include other academic programs, year levels, or even practicing teachers to compare shopping motivations across groups. They may also incorporate additional variables such as stress, academic workload, personality traits, or digital literacy to gain a deeper understanding of what drives impulse buying among students. Employing more advanced statistical techniques or conducting longitudinal studies may also offer richer insights into the changing patterns of online consumer behavior.

Declarations

Acknowledgements: The current study would like to express sincere gratitude to the Undergraduate Research Coordinator of the School of Teacher Education and Liberal Arts, Dr. Keven John N. Allit for the guidance and supervision provided to the student researchers. The authors are very thankful to all their schoolmates who voluntarily provided their responses and observations to the questions posted in the study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) Use Statement: The authors declare that no artificial intelligence (AI) tools or software were used in the research, analysis, or preparation of this manuscript. All work presented is entirely the original effort of the authors.

Author Contributions: NJC and RDP: Development and framing of the entire research; MLB: Adviser and consultant, editor, evaluator of all manuscript and research content; theories and concepts in the study. KJNA: External adviser and consultant, evaluator.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Consent to Publish: All authors agree to publish the paper in International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research.

Data Availability Statement: The data sets generated and/or analysed during this study are not publicly available but are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Funding: This research is not in any way under any funding agency or institution.

Institutional Review Board Statement: This study was conducted in accordance with the course requirements of the subject SS 212-Trends and Issues in Social Studies. We have taken approval from the Department Head of Professional Education to conduct this classroom-based research work through the approved course syllabi. During the conduct of this research, no ethics committee approval for undergraduate research was required at our institution.

Informed Consent Statement: Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in this study.

Research Content: The research content of this manuscript is original and has not been published elsewhere.

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Citation: Nylener Jayson Cabauatan, Robert Dela Peña, Marilyn L. Balmeo and Keven John N. Allit. 2026. Motivation and Impulse in E-Shopping Among Pre-Service Teachers: Needs-Based vs. Wants-Based. *International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research*, 10(1): 48-56.

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